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Preprint Version

Analysis of model parallelism applications on a 64-core RV64 Server CPU

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Abstract

Massive Data Parallel workloads, driven by inference on large ML models, are pushing hardware vendors to develop efficient and cost-effective multi-core server CPUs. The RISC-V architecture plays a prominent role due to its open, extensible, and energy-friendly ISA. Despite significant progress in recent years, finding efficient methods to run parallel applications on new architectures to harness their maximum performance fully remains a challenge. In this study, we benchmark the inference of machine learning models on the SOPHON SG2042 SoC, the first server-grade CPU based on the RV64 ISA, composed of 64 cores arranged in a grid of 16 groups of 4 cores. Specifically, we aim to enhance performance via better cache hit ratios stemming from model parallelism to split and assign parts of the model to specific (groups of) cores using a pipeline execution. We orchestrate execution using FastFlow, a low-level programming framework designed for multithreaded streaming applications. By comparing the results against the standard multi-core inference and analyzing the effects of different submodel-to-core mapping strategies, we aim to provide a comprehensive understanding of how the model parallel approach can maximize efficiency and utilization of hardware resources. In our experiments, using model parallelism improved up to 8.4 times the performance over the native PyTorch parallelism.

1 Introduction

Both scientific and artificial intelligence-derived applications are pushing manufacturers to develop increasingly efficient and cost-effective hardware [1]. Alongside this need is the increasingly insistent demand to reduce power consumption. In this scenario, the open standard RISC-V (reduced instruction-set computer-five) architecture plays a prominent role because it traditionally produces more performance while consuming less power than the complex instruction computer (CISC)-based ISA.

Although much progress has been made in the past few years, finding efficient ways to run parallel applications on these new architectures and exploiting the maximum performance that can be obtained remains a significant challenge. Resource allocation strategy, data communication efficiency, parallelism configuration, and other factors can highly impact performance. This is especially true when dealing with new architectures and processor designs. Here, in particular, we consider the SOPHON SG2042 RISC-V CPU. This is a 64-core processor divided into 16 clusters of 4 RISC-V C910 CPU cores each. Each core has 64KB of private L1 cache plus 1MB of L2 cache shared at cluster level. Clusters are interconnected via a grid to each other and to 64MB of last-level cache, using 4 DDR memory controllers and 32 Gen4 PCIe lanes.

Extracting the maximum performance of an architecture such as the SOPHON SG2042 is not trivial. Besides, a new, more powerful 64-core RISC-V CPU (SOPHON SG2044) has already been announced, and it is expected to be available to consumers in the near future [2]. SiFive, for example, recently introduced its new SiFive Performance P870-D processor, designed specifically for AI and highly parallelisable workloads, with scalability up to 256 cores [3]. Numerous other companies and initiatives are also rapidly advancing the development of new and more powerful RISC-V CPUs. Therefore, exploring modern workloads in these emerging architectures is paramount to driving and boosting advancements in hardware and software systems for RISC-V.

This study evaluates the performance for the specific case of high impact on how to best perform model inference on such an architecture. In particular, we compare model parallel against data parallel and mixed approaches. The inherent rationale is that the growing size of AI models puts increasing stress on the memory subsystem known to increasingly become the bottleneck in compute architectures [4]. Hence, adopting a layer-wise execution, where each layer is significantly smaller than the whole model, relieves the pressure on the memory bandwidth by increasing the data locality. To demonstrate this idea, we developed a small prototype application based on the FastFlow parallel programming library that can execute split Pytorch models in a pipeline fashion. Moreover, the application allows easy mapping of the different layers to (groups of) cores. Using this platform, we test different mapping strategies in the search to optimize the inference performance.

The main contributions of this work can be summarized as follows:

- We devise a pipelined execution of deep machine learning model inference tasks. This execution pattern better fits the cache hierarchy of modern CPUs and adds a new model parallelism dimension to inference tasks.
- We test the approach on the novel 64-core high-performance RISC-V-based SOPHON SG2042 processor across four modern computer vision models.

Fig. 1: Overview of the internal architecture of the SOPHON SG2042 SoC: a grid interconnects 16 clusters of 4 cores and 64MB of distributed L3 system level cache (SLC) cache.

- We evaluate how the load size impacts the inference performance of four ML models on a multicore RISC-V CPU.

This paper is organized as follows. Section §2 introduces the RISC-V processor, the platform, and the libraries used in this work. Related work is presented in Section §3. In Section §4, we discuss the experimental methodology. Results are presented and discussed in Section §5. We draw conclusions and final considerations in Section §6.

2 Background

2.1 SOPHON SG2042 SoC

The SG2042 system on-chip (SoC) contains 64 RISC-V cores divided into 16 clusters connected through a grid network. Each cluster comprises a XuanTie C920 4-core RISC-V CPU. Each core is equipped with 64KB of L1 instruction and data cache, and each cluster of 4 cores shares a 1MB of L2 cache. The unified L2 cache can handle two access requests in parallel within one cycle. The grid interconnect finally offers access to 64MB of level 3 cache shared among all 64 cores. Four DDR4-3200 memory controllers manage access to the main memory system. For peripherals, the SG2042 is equipped with 32 PCIe Gen4 lanes.

2.2 C920 RISC-V CPU

The XuanTie C920 [5] is a homogeneous high-performance 64-bit multi-core RISC-V CPU architecture designed by T-Head that supports 1 to 4 cores at a maximum operation frequency of 2 GHz. It targets high-performance applications and implements a 12-stage, out-of-order, multiple-issue superscalar pipeline. Based on the RISC-V instruction set architecture (ISA), this CPU provides the RV64GCV instructions [6].

2.3 Milk-V Pioneer Execution Platform

Milk-V Pioneer Box is a commercial and ready-to-use development platform in the form of a desktop computer. It is equipped with a Pioneer motherboard powered by the SOPHON SG2042. It was designed to provide a native development environment for developers and researchers. It eliminates or reduces the need to use different platforms to cross-compile programs for the RISC-V architecture. The one we use in this paper has 128GB of RAM DDR4 (3200MHz) and a 1TB PCIe 3.0 SSD. The operating system is Linux fedora-riscv 6.1.31.

2.4 Data and Model Parallelism

Model parallelism is a model inference technique for distributing the computational workload of a neural network across multiple devices or processors. Data parallelism is commonly used in traditional parallel computing. From a basic perspective, it concurrently runs the same computation over subsets of the workload in different processors. In the context of machine learning, copies of the model are run on each processor with different subsets of data. In contrast, model parallelism splits the model’s layers across different devices or processors, allowing each device to handle a portion of the model’s computations. Figure 2 shows an example applied to the `resnet18` model [7] for computer vision. Model parallelism distributes the model layers among the CPU clusters, while data parallelism replicates the entire model on each cluster. In both cases, streams of images are processed in a pipeline fashion. Model parallelism is particularly useful when dealing with large models that do not fit into the memory of a single device or when certain parts of the model require specialized hardware. By partitioning the model and distributing its computations, model parallelism enables training and inference on larger models that would otherwise be impractical to process on a single device.

2.5 FastFlow

To explore NUMA effects on the SOPHON SG2042 architecture, we used FastFlow [8, 9] to map threads to specific cores. FastFlow [8, 9] is a parallel programming library implemented using modern C++. Based on building blocks, parallelism with FastFlow is highly composable and reconfigurable. It provides high-level structured parallel patterns such as map, reduce, pipeline, and Farm. It targets applications that can be implemented as a directed graph of processing nodes, such as dataflow streaming networks, which directly map to most (if not all) modern deep neural network architectures, e.g., as leveraged by ONNX [10].

Fig. 2: Representation of model and data parallelism techniques.

This work uses the FastFlow pipeline parallel pattern to implement a linear directed graph of FastFlow nodes. In a pipeline, every stage/node works in a consumer/producer fashion. The pipeline stage receives a piece of data from a previous stage, applies some computation over it, and sends the data to the next stage, repeating this process until no more data is available. The exception is the first and last stages, which only produce or consume data. All the pipeline stages run concurrently, and FastFlow implements a buffer between each pair of stages where the stages can consume and store the produced data. Therefore, data is processed as soon as it is generated or arrives from an external source. Usually, the memory can be freed up as soon as the data is processed in the final stage. Thus, pipeline parallelism may be used to reduce the peak memory usage of an application. However, memory usage is highly tied to the number of stages, the size of the inter-stage buffers, and the load balance in FastFlow [11].

In the application, we used the `ff::ff_pipeline` directive, and every pipeline stage/node is a `ff::ff_node_t`. The communication among nodes is done through Single-Producer and Single-Consumer unidirectional and asynchronous lock-free FIFO (first in, first out) queues carrying memory pointers. These buffers/queues are implemented internally in the FastFlow library.

In FastFlow, tasks are statically executed by dedicated threads. This execution model contrasts with dynamic task schedulers implemented in other libraries, such as Threading Building Blocks (TBB). While dynamic execution models may perform better with general applications, FastFlow’s execution model allows more flexibility in building custom graphs and configurations, delegating the load balancing to the users. These FastFlow capabilities of fine-tuning configurations allow it to reach better throughput and latency performances in many scenarios [12].

Thanks to the flexibility provided by FastFlow’s execution model, it includes an internal library that allows users to map threads to specific CPUs. It can be used to fine-tune a program to control data locality and improve the efficiency of memory

accesses. This is a particularly important feature for this work since the SOPHON SG2042 RISC-V CPU architecture is subdivided into 16 clusters of C910 CPUs connected through a mesh network. This implies that data sharing among CPU clusters can add performance overheads, and thread/node placement should be considered.

Another fine-tuning mechanism FastFlow provides is the possibility of enabling a blocking behaviour to the threads. By default, FastFlow operates in non-blocking mode, meaning idle threads are always busy waiting in a spinlock. This is not a big issue in a pipeline with an ideal load balance since threads are not idle during most of the execution. However, such an ideal scenario is rare; in most cases, pipeline stages must wait for a slower stage. By enabling blocking mode in FastFlow, idle threads go to a sleep mode and free up computational resources, which can be used by other threads or as a strategy to reduce energy consumption, for instance. However, blocking mode is not always a good strategy since the time to wake threads also incurs performance penalties. In our test cases, this performance penalty was negligible since wake up time is significantly smaller than the execution time of any of the tested models (or pieces thereof). Therefore, we enabled blocking mode for the FastFlow applications we use in this work.

2.6 PyTorch Multi-threaded parallelisation

PyTorch exploits parallelisation on different application levels. This paper focuses on multi-threaded parallelisation of model inference [13]. Typically, a single shared thread pool of inference threads processes different inputs. By default, each of these threads executes the model’s operations sequentially inline. However, the model can exploit parallelism, forking its operations on different tasks. This level of parallelism is named inter-op parallelism and is handled by the global atomic integer variables `num_interop_threads`. The framework can exploit another level of parallelism, intra-op parallelism, to compute the most intensive operations like convolutions and matrix multiplications in parallel. This level of parallelism is controlled by another atomic integer global variable `num_threads`. These operations can be carried out at the lower level using different Linear algebra libraries, such as OpenBLAS [14], EIGEN [15], and OneDNN [16], for multi-threading execution.

3 Related Work

Colonnelli et al. [17] started porting the PyTorch Deep Learning framework [18] to RISC-V architectures. Specifically, they ported the Chromium Breakpad library, the SLEEF vector math library, and the PyTorch CPU INFOrmation library (`cpuinfo`) to RISC-V. Thanks to this porting, the authors could compile and test PyTorch v2.0 on the SiFive Freedom U740 SoC machine. They tested applications provided by the default PyTorch benchmark. More specifically, for training, the `regression` and `mnist` applications were chosen. For inference, `imagenet` was used with different image classification models. The authors concluded the work by asserting that the porting of PyTorch to RISC-V is mature for research and development applications.

Mittone et al. [19] show a methodology to implement a flexible and decentralized learning scheme in a distributed way, mixing FastFlow and PyTorch. The

work evaluates Federated Learning and Edge Inference applications on different distributed systems, characterized by different Instruction Set Architecture (ISA): Monte Cimone [20], a RISC-V computer cluster, and an EPI-TO system [21], composed by 4 ARM-v8 nodes, 4 x86-64 nodes, and 2 RISC-V nodes. The work shows a difference of about one order of magnitude in the performance of RISC-V compared with Intel/ARM CPUs. Differently from that, we deeply investigate the cache effects of splitting model layers across the system’s cores.

There are a couple of works [22, 23] evaluating single-precision floating-point RISC-V Vector instructions using RAJA Performance Suite (RAJAperf). Comparisons were made using three different systems: Allwinner D1, based on a C906 RISC-V processor with RVV v0.7.1 with 128-bit vector registers, StarFive Vision Five V2 board, a quad-core SiFive U74 RISC-V processor and Fujitsu A64FX, an Arm-v8 processor that supports SIMD fixed length and vector length SVE, instruction sets. Results show that some benchmark applications compiled with vector instructions are up to 80% faster than the scalar alternative.

Lepers et al. [24] analyze the impact of NUMA asymmetric topology on a commercial x86 system. In particular, the authors show that the asymmetry of the interconnect in modern NUMA systems drastically impacts performance. In these architectures, the bandwidth affects the performance more than the node’s distance. Unlike that, we used AI applications as test cases to analyse performance on the newer RISC-V 64 cores architecture.

4 Experimental Methodology

4.1 Application

We compared the model against data parallelism using a traditional inference problem. Using Fastflow, we developed an application to execute part of a trained machine-learning model on a subset of the machine’s cores. In order to do this in parallel, the original inference model was split into several layers, which are executed by FastFlow nodes organized through a pipeline parallel pattern. A sketch of the application can be seen in Figure 3. Listing 1 shows how the pipeline is filled by FastFlow nodes. Specifically, the object `ff_pipeline` was filled using the `add_stage` method. The first node in the pipeline, called the emitter, initiates the image stream. The last node in the pipeline, called sink, collects the results. Each of the other intermediate stages of the pipeline executes one layer of the model.

```
int main(int argc, char *argv[]){
    ff::ffTime(ff::START_TIME);
    // reads batches, batch size, path to model and cores binding files

    // Create pipeline with emitter node (NodeI), model nodes and sink node (NodeO)
    ff::ff_pipeline pipeline;
    pipeline.add_stage(new RandomIn(batches, {batchsize,3,224,224}, emitter_cpu.cpu
    ));
    int i=0;
    for (const auto& lay : layers) {
        pipeline.add_stage(new NetNode(lay, i, worker_cpus[i].cpu));
        ++i;
    }
    pipeline.add_stage(new NodeOut(sink_cpu.cpu));
}
```

```

// Run pipeline
if (pipeline.run_and_wait_end() < 0) {
    ff::error("Error while executing: pipeline\n");
    return -1;
}
std::cout<<"Time (s) to execute the pipeline: "<<pipeline.ffTime()*1e-3<<std::
endl;
std::cout<<"Time (s) to execute svc method in the pipeline: "<<pipeline.
ffwTime()*1e-3<<std::endl;
ff::ffTime(ff::STOP_TIME);
std::cout<<"Time (s) to execute entire application: "<<ff::ffTime(ff::GET_TIME)
*1e-3<< std::endl;
}

```

Listing 1: Pipeline

Listing 2 shows the structure of these layer nodes. The `svc_init` method initializes the node by assigning cores and loading the model (or layer thereof) into the `net` variable. The cores to use are passed via the input arguments and set using the routine `ff_mapThreadToCpus`, which generates a CPU mask using the Linux system call `sched_setaffinity`. Every FastFlow node can span a pool of threads to execute on the subset of cores. To do it, it was necessary to slightly modify the `aten` parallel PyTorch library. In particular, we modified the variable `num_threads` (§2.6) making it `thread_local`. The `svc` method processes the input images by executing the pre-loaded layers using the `forward` method.

```

class NetNode : public ff::ff_node_t<message> {
private:
    // vars
    Net <torch::jit::Module> *net;
    torch::Device device{torch::kCPU};
    ...
public:
    //constructors and destructors
    ...

    int svc_init() {
        // Setting cpu number of cores and mapping
        num_cores = ff_mapThreadToCpus(cpu_id.c_str());
        ...
        // load model layer
        net = (new Net<torch::jit::Module>(model_path));
        net->to(device);
        return (num_cores < 0);
    }

    message* svc(message *input){
        // execute model layer
        msg = new message(net->forward(input->data.to(device)));
        delete input;
        ff_send_out(msg);
        return GO_ON;
    }
};

```

Listing 2: Layers

Fig. 3: The pipeline structure of the application used.

We chose four classical computer vision deep models: `squeezenet1` [25], `vgg11` [26], `resnet18` and `resnet512` [7]. These models are commonly used to classify images. `squeezenet1`, `vgg`, and `resnet` identify three well-known deep neural network architecture families, whereas the number identifies a specific model size within the family. The VGG model was introduced in 2014 during the year’s ImageNet Large-Scale Visual Recognition Challenge (ILSVRC). Differently from [27, 28], it uses smaller convolution filters (3×3) to improve accuracy and performance. The following year’s edition of ILSVRC presented the Resnet model that mitigates the well-known problem of the vanishing gradient [29, 30]. The model uses the “shortcut connections” `shortcut1`, `shortcut2`, which allow gradients to flow through the network, facilitating training. SqueezeNet1 model is a lightweight convolutional neural network designed to achieve high accuracy using significantly fewer parameters [25]. The small number of parameters improves scalability because fewer communications are needed and require less memory, so it allows new architectures such as those of mobile, embedded, and FPGA devices to be exploited and is easily portable.

Table 1: Main characteristics of the models

	<code>squeezenet1</code>	<code>vgg11</code>	<code>resnet18</code>	<code>resnet512</code>
#Layers	18	30	15	57
#Nparam	1,235,496	132,863,336	11,689,512	60,192,808
#GFLOPS	0.7051	15.2392	3.6362	23.0945
MACs(GMACs)	0.3491	7.6091	1.8141	11.5136

Although different, all three families at a high level can be divided into layers where each layer only receives inputs from the previous layer and provides its outputs only to the next layer. This connection offers a natural choice to cut the model into pieces and mapping these pieces to stages in a pipeline to achieve model parallelism. The models differ in the number, type and size of the layers. This directly affects the compute and memory footprint of each model and their layers. Details of the models can be found in Table 1. To validate our application, we use real input images from a

dataset directory. Specifically, we used a subset of the ImageNet dataset [31]. We then executed the application using both the complete and partitioned models, ensuring that the predictions were equal in each case.

4.2 Models' Splitting and Binding Strategies

Fig. 4: Layers splitting and binding on resnet18 and squeezeNet1

Fig. 4: Layers splitting and binding on vgg11 and resnet152

For splitting the models, we decomposed them into the individual layers of each one. The layers can be executed in parallel as stages of a pipeline, and each stage can have internal data parallelism. Based on the split models, we implemented four distinct binding strategies for pinning the layers’ threads to specific processing cores. The entire (non-split) model, which is the native parallelism of PyTorch, would be identified as `entire_m` in the following sections. In this section, we explain the binding strategies we implemented for the split models: `FLOPs_bind`, `no_intercluster`, `overlap2`, and `overlap4`.

The `FLOPs_bind` binding strategy is the main one, and the other three derive from it. For this strategy, we first used the Python package `callops` v0.0.2 to estimate the number of floating-point operations (FLOPs) required by each layer of a specific model. Since all model layers are executed in a pipelined fashion, to maximize the performance (i.e., minimize cores stalled for lack of input work), we try to balance the load between all pipeline stages by assigning a number of cores to each pipeline stage, such that the estimated run time, i.e., $FLOPs/\#cores$ ratio, is approximately the same. In addition to the load balancing, we added to `FLOPs_bind` two additional rules: 1) each layer should be assigned at least one core, and 2) cores are not shared across layers to maximize the private cache available to that layer. Figure 4 shows how we bound the layers’ threads for the four models across the 64 cores using this parallelism strategy. In all cases for this first strategy, we reserve core number 0 for the emitter node injecting the input data and core number 63 for the sink node collecting the results.

Figure 4a represents the binding of the `resnet18` model layers. This model was split into 15 layers. Specifically, layer 1 is a convolutional layer that demands 236 MFLOPs; we execute this layer on cores 1-7. Layer 2 is a batch normalization layer

requiring 1.61 MFLOPs; we assign cores 8-10. Layers 2 and 3 are relu and max pooling layers; they need a small number of FLOPs, so we assigned them to cores 11 and 12. The next eight layers represent a block in the resnet architecture and are the most expensive; they require roughly 400 MFLOPs each and are composed of a convolution, a batch normalization, and a relu activation. We decided to assign six cores to each one. The last three layers have a low FLOP count, so we allocated one core each.

Figure 4b represents the distribution of the layers of the `squeezenet1` model. This model was split into 18 layers. Specifically, layer 1 is a convolutional layer with 43 MFLOPs; we assigned two cores. Layers 2 and 3 are relu and max pooling layers; they do not require many FLOPs, so we assigned them to cores 3 and 4. Layers 4 and 5 are compound layers, consisting of 3 convolutions interspersed with three relu activations. We call these layers fire layer. They require 69 and 75 MFLOPs, so we assigned six cores each, from core 5 to core 10 and from core 11 to core 16. Layer 6 is a max pooling layer that does not require many FLOPs, so we assigned core 17. The next three layers follow the same pattern. Layers 10 and 11 are fire layers that demand 35 MFLOPs, while layers 12 and 13, fire again, require 63 MFLOPs. We assigned 4 and 6 cores, respectively. Layer 14 is a dropout layer; it is very lightweight, so we assigned one core. Layer 15 is a convolutional layer that requires 173 MFLOPs; we assigned eight cores, from 52 to 59. Layers 16, 17, and 18 are relu, adaptive average pooling, and flatten; they require few FLOPs, so we assigned one core each.

Figure 4c represents the binding of the layers of the `vgg11` model. This model was split into 30 layers. Layer 1 is a convolutional layer requiring 176 MFLOPs; we assigned cores 1 and 2. The next two layers are relu and max pooling layers; they do not require many FLOPs, so we assigned one core each. The following three layers have the same structure, the only difference being that the convolutional layer requires 1850 MFLOPs. We assigned four cores to this layer and one cores to the others. Layer 7 is a convolutional layer requiring 1850 MFLOPs; a relu layer follows it. Layer 9 is a convolutional layer requiring 3700 MFLOPs followed by relu and a max pooling layer. We assigned 4 and 8 cores to the convolutional layers and one core to the other layers. From 12 to 16 layers, the structure is the same, and the MFLOPs required by the convolutional layers are also the same, so we assigned the same number of cores. The structure of layers 17-21 is the same, but the number of FLOPs required by the convulsive layers differs. Specifically, each convolutional layer requires 924 MFLOPs. We assigned four cores to each of these. Layers 22 and 23 are adaptive average pooling and flattened layers; they do not require many FLOPs, so we allocated one core each. Layers 24, 25, and 26 are, respectively, linear, relu, and dropout layers. The linear layer requires 205 MFLOPs; we assigned two cores. To the other two layers, we assigned one core. Layers 27, 28, and 29 follow the same scheme, and we assign the same number of cores. Layer 30 is a linear layer requiring 8 MFLOPs. Thus, we assigned a single core to it.

Figure 4d represents the distribution of the layers of the `resnet512` model. This model was split into 57 layers. Regarding the number of FLOPs, this model is the largest we have used; it takes around 23 GFLOPs to process. Since the model was split into 57 layers, we were limited to assigning different core partitions, having only 64

cores. However, 50 layers comprise convolutional, batch normalization, and relu sub-layers. Each of them requires about 430 MFLOPs, except for a couple that require 730 MFLOPs. We assign one core for each of the former layers and two for the latter.

The second, third, and fourth binding strategies use the same model-splitting strategy but with different CPU bindings. We omit the visual mappings for sake of space. The second binding strategy, which we call `no_intercluster` (short for “no layers intercluster”), rules that no layer should run threads on different clusters. Each cluster on the SG2042 architecture comprises four cores sharing a 1 MB L2 cache, as described in §2.1. Therefore, this strategy seeks to keep the data sharing of each layer’s threads on the L2 cache. If a layer runs a thread on a different cluster, any communication will require operations on L3, which is costly and may not compensate if the amount of synchronization demanded by the threads is high. The consequence of applying this rule is that the layers running more than four threads on the first strategy now run only four, but all in the same cluster. Layers running less than four threads now may run up to four, depending on how many cores are available on its cluster.

The third and fourth binding strategies break out rule number two of the `FLOPs_bind` strategy, which states that cores should not be assigned to more than one layer. The downside effect of this rule is that light layers in a pipeline tend to be idle most of the time, waiting for previous or next pipeline stages to complete their work. Since these idle layers are exclusively assigned to a core, this core would also be idle. This issue does not happen with the native parallelism (entire model). Hence, we created a strategy of overlapping layers, which means extending the assigned number of cores to each layer so two or more layers can share a number of cores, overlapping each other’s “domains” previously defined by the `FLOPs_bind`. We run the models with the `overlap2` and `overlap4` strategies. In `overlap2`, each layer can run two more threads on two extra adjacent cores. For instance, if in `FLOPs_bind` a layer was bound to cores 3-5, with `overlap2`, it can run threads on cores 2-6. Therefore, each layer will share at least two cores with adjacent layers. The last strategy, `overlap2`, follows the same principle but shares four adjacent cores with adjacent layers, two at the bottom and two at the top boundaries.

4.3 Execution Environment

We compiled PyTorch [18] version 2.3.0 from scratch using the modifications introduced by Colonnelli et al. [17]. The base compiler was `gcc version 13.2` [32] with the flag `-O2`. The C++ standard used was 2017. We built the library with the option `USE_OPENMP=1`, which enables OpenMP version 4.5. We added the option `USE_MKLDNN=1`, which enables the library Intel(R) MKL-DNN v3.3.2 [16]. As BLAS (Basic Linear Algebra Subprograms) library, we used BLIS [33] version 3.0. We built the library in Release mode. Please note that here we do not yet leverage the RVV 0.7.1 support from the C910 cores.

Our application is written in C++ and compiled with `g++ version 13.2`. We read a JSON file to specify the cores assigned to each layer. The application parses the file using the cereal C++ library [34]. The application was built using `cmake version 3.27.4`. We execute the tests on the system with `Linux Fedora Kernel 6.1.31`.

Table 2: resnet18 model inference performance with the entire model (native PyTorch parallelism) and split model parallelism with four different binding strategies.

Batches	Size	Average execution time (s)				
		entire_m	FLOPs_bind	no_intercluster	overlap2	overlap4
1	1	2.70±0.14	2.38±0.09	2.27±0.02	2.51±0.18	2.52±0.26
1	10	4.88±0.09	12.58±1.94	12.91±0.06	9.21±0.66	8.06±0.39
10	1	9.73±0.26	3.75±0.32	5.89±0.13	5.80±0.29	6.17±0.37
10	10	33.51±1.16	25.19±1.65	29.83±0.16	25.39±0.95	25.51±0.81
100	1	65.95±3.07	15.28±0.42	34.32±0.39	32.83±1.29	34.28±0.64
100	10	279.31±2.60	139.45±2.61	185.75±0.88	150.45±1.82	151.08±1.72

Table 3: squeezenet1 model inference performance with the entire_m (native PyTorch parallelism) and split model parallelism with four different binding strategies.

Batches	Size	Average execution time (s)				
		entire_m	FLOPs_bind	no_intercluster	overlap2	overlap4
1	1	1.68±0.05	1.20±0.01	1.26±0.01	1.33±0.10	1.32±0.07
1	10	3.05±0.23	4.89±0.03	3.92±0.08	3.36±0.09	2.90±0.12
10	1	9.45±0.54	2.13±0.02	2.42±0.14	2.79±0.11	3.01±0.14
10	10	24.79±1.82	12.01±0.25	10.36±0.13	11.88±0.44	11.11±0.25
100	1	75.84±1.34	9.02±0.09	10.40±0.54	11.96±0.98	12.91±0.54
100	10	196.84±1.75	81.88±1.39	67.18±2.59	65.70±1.26	62.14±1.63

5 Results

For each model, we performed a test varying the number of batches (1, 10, and 100) and the size of each batch (1 and 10). We compared the results of the entire model, executed on all cores and leaving the native parallelization of PyTorch, against the split model with the four binding strategies, as described in §4.2. Tables 2, 3, 4, and 5 show the models inference performance results. Specifically, it is the time in seconds taken by the application to execute the models with the different strategies for splitting and binding layers, including the native PyTorch execution (`entire_m`). We repeated each experiment 10 times, and the tables show the average execution time and the corresponding standard deviation.

Table 6 shows the performance ratio for all four binding strategies and the four models. Green-coloured cells are the cases where the custom binding strategies performed better than the native PyTorch parallelism ($\frac{t_{entire_m}}{t_{binding_strategy}} > 1$). In this table, it is possible to notice that the custom binding strategies with the split models performed better in most test cases. The table shows that the best batching configurations among the ones we tested are the ones with many smaller batches (10-1 and 100-1) that we can pipeline. These two configurations presented the highest ratio values and performed better than the native Torch parallelism with all four binding

Table 4: vgg11 model inference performance with the `entire_m` (native PyTorch parallelism) and split model parallelism with four different binding strategies.

Batches	Size	Average execution time (s)				
		<code>entire_m</code>	<code>FLOPs_bind</code>	<code>no_intercluster</code>	<code>overlap2</code>	<code>overlap4</code>
1	1	11.09±8.04	8.81±1.23	8.46±1.02	7.00±3.90	15.40±10.5
1	10	12.10±6.90	58.59±15.9	57.55±11.5	38.70±4.40	30.31±1.68
10	1	36.93±4.72	13.62±0.31	13.73±0.31	14.09±6.57	13.46±5.63
10	10	96.84±7.74	96.73±5.03	122.55±2.92	85.84±1.77	89.04±7.73
100	1	208.56±11.1	78.55±0.80	85.28±1.55	70.36±4.13	73.95±4.48
100	10	769.82±36.6	607.51±5.68	835.72±5.18	568.12±5.67	584.32±11.5

Table 5: resnet152 model inference performance with the `entire_m` (native PyTorch parallelism) and split model parallelism with four different binding strategies.

Batches	Size	Average execution time (s)				
		<code>entire_m</code>	<code>FLOPs_bind</code>	<code>no_intercluster</code>	<code>overlap2</code>	<code>overlap4</code>
1	1	11.45±2.00	28.52±0.38	35.07±0.51	21.40±0.78	17.05±0.79
1	10	34.06 ±0.42	202.57±0.65	274.79±5.82	122.87±1.54	78.32±1.96
10	1	64.99±1.50	33.77±0.09	47.33±0.53	45.91±1.05	43.15±0.71
10	10	310.68±0.72	249.69±1.81	380.63±2.00	253.42±6.71	231.57±4.58
100	1	488.25±12.6	154.22±55.3	135.00±2.09	188.73±6.57	200.68±4.75
100	10	2823.93±27.9	990.29±357	1266.01±13.1	921.79±6.92	902.80±6.00

strategies with all the models. The best result was `squeezenet1`, with 100 1-sized batches and `FLOPs_bind` strategy, which improved the performance by 8.41 times.

When running the models with a single 10-sized batch as input, all the binding strategies failed to improve the performance over the native Torch in most models. The worst result was the `no_intercluster` strategy with the `resnet152` model. It was 8.4 times slower than the native Torch parallelism. Regarding the results for 1 batch with 1 sample, we attribute the positive ratio to a more efficient use of the cache. Overall, the binding strategy that performed the worst was the `no_intercluster` one. This means that bounding the layer threads to a single cluster to keep most of the data communication for the intra-parallelism on the L2 cache may be used only in more specific scenarios than the other strategies. However, it still performed better than the native Torch parallelism in 67% of the tested cases. Regarding the `Overlap2` and `Overlap4` binding strategies, both presented similar performance results and better results than the `FLOPs_bind` one in many cases. It is noteworthy that `resnet18` and `squeezenet1` models presented a positive ratio in more tests than `vgg1` and `resnet152`. This is because the first two models have a smaller memory footprint than the other two. Hence, they better fit in the cache, causing fewer cache misses and consequently avoiding the overhead of fetching the data from a higher cache level or main memory.

On the results presented in Table 6, the splitting and binding strategies performed better than the native Torch parallelism in around 75% of the test cases. Our custom

Table 6: Execution time (t) ratio of `entire_m` (native PyTorch parallelism) versus the four binding strategies ($\frac{t_{entire_m}}{t_{binding_strategy}}$), varying the number of batches and the number of images per batch.

Model	Batches	Batch size	$\frac{t_{entire_m}}{t_{FLOPs_bind}}$	$\frac{t_{entire_m}}{t_{no_intercluster}}$	$\frac{t_{entire_m}}{t_{overlap2}}$	$\frac{t_{entire_m}}{t_{overlap4}}$
resnet18	1	1	1.13	1.19	1.07	1.07
	1	10	0.39	0.38	0.53	0.61
	10	1	2.59	1.65	1.68	1.58
	10	10	1.33	1.12	1.32	1.31
	100	1	4.31	1.92	2.01	1.92
	100	10	2.01	1.50	1.86	1.85
squeezenet1	1	1	1.39	1.33	1.26	1.28
	1	10	0.62	0.78	0.91	1.05
	10	1	4.42	3.90	3.39	3.14
	10	10	2.06	2.39	2.09	2.23
	100	1	8.41	7.29	6.34	5.88
	100	10	2.41	2.93	3.00	3.17
vgg11	1	1	1.26	1.31	1.58	0.72
	1	10	0.20	0.21	0.31	0.40
	10	1	2.71	2.69	2.62	2.74
	10	10	1.01	0.79	1.13	1.09
	100	1	2.65	2.45	2.96	2.82
	100	10	1.27	0.92	1.36	1.32
resnet152	1	1	0.4	0.33	0.54	0.67
	1	10	0.17	0.12	0.28	0.43
	10	1	1.92	1.37	1.42	1.51
	10	10	1.24	0.82	1.23	1.34
	100	1	3.17	3.62	2.59	2.43
	100	10	2.85	2.23	3.06	3.13

strategies struggle to get better performance when processing very small loads. This is because the splitting strategy relies on pipeline parallelism, which is more efficient with stream-like workloads with small data items. The pipeline parallelism acts at the inter-batch level. Each pipeline stage processes a different batch in parallel, whereas PyTorch acts at the intra-batch level, parallelizing the computation across the different samples of a batch. Increasing the number of batches helps to run more pipeline stages in parallel, while increasing the number of samples per batch best takes advantage of the cores assigned to each pipeline stage. In addition, increasing the number of batches attenuates the impact of idle pipeline stages at the computation’s beginning and end. Therefore, in the evaluated scenarios, our strategies should perform best with 100 batches with one (100-1) image per batch and worst with a single batch with ten images (1-10). As expected, the 100-1 strategy presented the highest performance results because it is the only one with enough data items to fill the pipelines on their entirety during execution.

6 Conclusions

This work analyzes the performance of a typical deep machine learning model inference application on a modern HPC RISC-V architecture. Specifically, we compared the model’s performance using only data parallelism to the performance of the same model split into layers executed in a pipeline fashion via FastFlow. As expected, splitting the model into different layers, and executing them in a pipeline fashion, performed better than executing the entire model when we have a stream of batches because each layer better fits the cache, and the pipeline offers an additional level of (model) parallelism. We also evaluated four strategies to bind the layers (pipeline stages) to specific cores. In general, all strategies performed better than the entire model execution with enough batches to pipeline. However, the best strategy depends on the mix of stream length, i.e., number of batches and batch size, which may make it quite challenging for machine learning application programmers to select or implement one strategy. In the future, we would like to do an in-depth analysis of the effects of caching using tools such as Performance Counters for Linux [35]. To this point, such tools provide limited support for the current RISC-V architectures available. It would also be essential to evaluate the energy consumption of these models and the tested strategies. In addition, in future work, we may also investigate the performance impact of using or not the silicon-enabled RISC-V Vectors already implemented in new RISC-V CPUs that are commercially available, including the one we used in this work.

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